

**REGULATORY FRAMEWORK OF TECHNOLOGIES FOR STUDYING
READING, MATHEMATICS AND NATURAL-SCIENTIFIC LITERACY
THROUGH THE INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAM FOR
ELEMENTARY STUDENTS**

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ANNOTATION

This article will talk about the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers in order to organize international research in the field of assessment of the quality of education in the Republican public education system, establish international relations, to comprehensively support and encourage the research and innovation activities of students and young people, above all, creative ideas and creativity of the younger generation.

Keywords: *International Assessment, PISA, PIRLS, TALIS, TIMSS.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье речь идет о постановлении Кабинета министров в целях организации международных исследований в области оценки качества образования в системе народного образования республики, установления международных связей, всесторонней поддержки и стимулирования научно-

исследовательской и инновационной деятельности учащихся и молодежи, прежде всего творческих идей и творчества подрастающего поколения.

Ключевые слова: международная оценка, PISA, PIRLS, TALIS, TIMSS.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada respublika xalq ta'limi tizimida ta'lim sifatini baholash sohasidagi xalqaro tadqiqotlarni tashkil etish, xalqaro aloqalarni o'rnatish, o'quvchi-yoshlarning ilmiy-tadqiqot va innovatsiya faoliyatini, eng avvalo, yosh avlodning ijodiy g'oyalari va ijodkorligini har tomonlama qo'llab-quvvatlash hamda rag'batlantirish maqsadida Vazirlar Mahkamasining qarori haiqda so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Xalqaro baholash, PISA, PIRLS, TALIS, TIMSS.

Several decisions were made by the Cabinet of Ministers in order to organize international research in the field of assessment of the quality of education in the Republican public education system, to establish international relations, to comprehensively support and encourage the research and innovation activities of students and young people, and above all, the creative ideas and creativity of the younger generation:

1. The state inspectorate of quality control of Education under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan (next called the Inspectorate of Education), the Ministry of public education, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and the Ministry of Finance:

(a) the organization of International Studies (referred to as International Studies) on the following international assessment programs:

Progress in International Reading and Literacy Study (PIRLS) to assess the level of reading and understanding of text by primary 4th graders;

Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) — to assess the level of assimilation of 4th and 8th graders in mathematics and natural orientation;

The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) is a 15 — year-old student's assessment of literacy in reading, mathematics and Natural Sciences;

The Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS) is a survey of the teaching and learning environment and the working conditions of teachers in general secondary educational institutions of the executive and pedagogical personnel;

b) the proposals of the State Inspectorate for quality control of Education under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan to establish the National Center for the implementation of international research on quality assessment of Education were approved.

2. The following were established as the main tasks and areas of activity of the National Center:

- ✚ participation as a representative of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the organization and coordination of international research;

- ✚ to conduct scientific research aimed at the development and introduction of innovative methods for the development of literacy in the educational system, mathematics and Natural Sciences;

- ✚ to establish international relations in the field of quality assessment of education, to develop and implement international projects, to participate in the organization and holding of international scientific conferences and symposia;

- ✚ conducting fundamental and Applied Research in the field of quality assessment of Education;

- ✚ scientific and methodological support of research on the assessment of the quality of Education;

- ✚ ensuring the successful participation of general secondary institutions in international research;

- ✚ Comparative comparison of the results of the Republic of Uzbekistan recorded in international assessment programs with the results of other countries;

✚ systematic monitoring of the introduction of international assessment programs into the educational process, popularization of advanced experience in this area and participation in the development of recommendations and manuals for educational institutions on its basis;

✚ preparation of educational and methodological recommendations for improving the skills of pedagogical personnel in the field of reading, mathematics and natural sciences using innovative teaching methods.

3. The following:

According to Appendix 1 “roadmap” on preparation for participation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in International Studies;

The structure of the National Center for the implementation of international research on the assessment of the quality of Education under the state inspectorate for quality control of Education under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan was approved in accordance with Appendix 2.

The head of the educational inspection, if necessary, was allowed to make changes to the structure of the National Center within the framework of the total limited number of employees and the remuneration fund.

From the above decisions, it can be concluded that through the program of international assessment of its students, reading, mathematics and natural-scientific literacy are considered to increase and further improve their framework of logical thinking. To do this, it is necessary, first of all, to use the overseas experiments that have shown us to high results.

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